

A Comprehensive Review of Potassium Extraction Methods from K-Feldspar

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Abstract

With the global population expected to reach 9.8 billion by 2050, increasing agricultural productivity to meet food demand is critical. Potassium is a vital macronutrient for plant growth, yet over 90% of potassium fertilizers come from water-soluble salts that constitute less than 1% of global potassium reserves. Potassium feldspar (KAlSi_3O_8), abundant and rich in potassium and alumina, presents a promising alternative source, but its extraction is hindered by low solubility and high processing costs. This review provides a comprehensive overview of various methods for extracting potassium from K-feldspar, including acid leaching, hydrothermal processing, roast-leaching, and microbiological techniques. It also highlights the role of ultrasound- and microwave-assisted methods as auxiliary approaches to improve extraction efficiency. The mechanisms, efficiencies, influencing parameters, and recent advancements of each method are comprehensively analyzed. Furthermore, this review also provides a detailed overview of statistical methods used to optimize high potassium extraction processes, aiming to reduce both costs and experimental effort through fewer experimental runs. Finally, the review outlines future research prospects and potential strategies for enhancing the efficient extraction of potassium from K-feldspar.

Keywords: *K-feldspar, potassium extraction, Acid leaching method, Hydrothermal method, Roast-leaching method.*

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Introduction

The global population is projected to reach approximately 9.8 billion by 2050, representing

an increase of nearly 2 billion people from current levels. To meet the corresponding rise in food demand, agricultural production must

increase significantly. Achieving this goal requires the sustainable use of land and natural resources, as intensifying cultivation without sustainability can lead to soil degradation and long-term yield loss. A critical component of sustainable agriculture is ensuring that crops receive the essential nutrients required for healthy growth and development. (Schueler et al., 2021)

Potassium is one of the three essential macronutrients required for plant growth, alongside nitrogen and phosphorus. In modern agriculture, potassium is predominantly supplied in the form of potassium chloride (KCl), which accounts for approximately 96% of global potassium fertilizer consumption, while the remaining 4% is provided by potassium nitrate (KNO₃) and potassium sulfate (K₂SO₄). (Jena, 2021a) More than 90% of potassium fertilizers are produced from conventional water-soluble potassium salts. However, these salts represent less than 1% of the global potassium reserves, underscoring a significant imbalance between resource availability and agricultural demand. (Zhao et al., 2020) The geographical distribution of water-soluble potassium resources is highly uneven, with a few countries controlling the majority of accessible reserves. Canada, Russia, and Belarus are among the top producers, exploiting extensive salt deposits and brine sources to extract potash. Together, these three countries possess over 2.25 billion tons (22.5 × 10⁸ t) of K₂O, accounting for roughly 57.5% of the world's total potassium reserves. Other notable contributors include Germany, Israel, and Jordan, which also rely on natural sources such as seawater and evaporate deposits for potash production. (Ciceri et al., 2015; Jena, 2021a; Shi et al., 2023)

Potassium can be obtained from both seawater and mineral sources. Common methods for recovering potassium from seawater include chemical precipitation, solvent extraction, membrane separation, and ion exchange. (Chen et al., 2018; Guo et al., 2016; Hou et al., 2013; Marinsky & Marcus, 1995; Pujiastuti et al., 2016; Sano et al., 2018) Over 180 types of processed potassium products are made from raw potassium salts due to their valuable physical and

chemical properties. Potassium resources are generally classified as either soluble or insoluble. (Zhenwu Ding et al., 2014) Soluble potassium minerals commonly used in agriculture include carnallite (KCl·MgCl₂·6H₂O), sylvite (KCl), langbeinite (K₂SO₄·2MgSO₄), kainite (KMg(SO₄)Cl·3H₂O), and polyhalite (K₂Ca₂Mg(SO₄)₄·2H₂O). In contrast, insoluble potassium-bearing minerals include orthoclase, microcline, muscovite, and leucite. (S. Jena, N. Dhawan, D. Rao, et al., 2016) Potassium can be extracted from minerals using three primary approaches: physical, chemical, and microbiological methods. Physical methods—such as magnetic separation, gravity separation, and flotation—rely on differences in physical properties to separate potassium-bearing minerals from other components. Chemical methods involve breaking down the mineral structure through reactions, with techniques like acid leaching and roasting followed by leaching commonly used when potassium is tightly bound within the crystal lattice. Microbiological methods employ specific microorganisms capable of decomposing minerals like K-feldspar, thereby releasing potassium in a bioavailable form. (Heyes et al., 2012) Among these, Solution mining is one of the easiest and most affordable ways to extract potassium from water-soluble salts like sylvite. It involves injecting hot water into underground potash deposits through one well. After some time, the potassium-rich brine is pumped out through another well for processing. This method is cheaper and causes less environmental damage than traditional mining. (Dahms & Edmonds, 1962) For example, In Saskatchewan, Canada, most high-grade potash deposits are located about 900 meters below the surface. Solution mining is commonly used here to extract potash from deep underground deposits that are unsuitable for conventional mining methods. Another widely used method is the evaporation of water from salt lakes and surface brines to recover potash salts. This technique is applied in places such as the Great Salt Lake and Bonneville Salt Flats in Utah, Searles Lake in California, and the Dead Sea region in Israel and Jordan. (Tanvar & Dhawan, 2022)

However, these resources are unevenly distributed and limited in many regions. (Ciceri et al., 2015; S. Jena, N. Dhawan, D. Rao, et al., 2016; Jena, 2021a) As a result, numerous agriculture-dependent countries lack domestic production capabilities and rely entirely on potash imports, often at high economic cost. For example, China has only about 2.2% of the world's water-soluble potassium, around 210 million tons of K_2O , which is a major shortage. As a result, nearly half of China's annual potash fertilizer consumption depends on imports. (Wang et al., 2018) In terms of global consumption trends, the use of potash in fertilizers increased from 35.7 million metric tons in 2022 to an estimated 37.1 million metric tons in 2023. Asia and South America continue to be the leading regions in potash consumption. To meet the rising demand, global potash production capacity is projected to increase from 64.3 million metric tons of K_2O in 2023 to approximately 67.6 million metric tons by 2026. (*Mineral commodity summaries 2024*, 2024) However, many countries in the Global South lack the domestic capacity to produce adequate quantities of potash to support their agricultural sectors. For instance, countries like India (about 3.5 million tons per annum) and Brazil are heavily reliant on imports, with over 90% of their potash needs sourced from international suppliers. (Ciceri et al., 2017; Tanvar & Dhawan, 2020) In contrast, Many countries and regions possess abundant reserves of water-insoluble K-feldspar, with total global resources estimated to exceed 10 billion tons. (Zhao et al., 2020) For example, China alone, the proven reserves of K-feldspar are estimated at 97 billion tons and India possesses substantial feldspar reserves, estimated at around 16 million tons. These feldspar deposits typically contain approximately 9–16% K_2O , indicating significant potential as a secondary source of potassium. (S. K. Jena et al., 2016)

Given these conditions, the development and utilization of potassium-rich ores represent a strategically significant approach to mitigating potassium deficiencies. Exploiting such alternative resources has the potential to substantially reduce reliance on imports and promote sustainable agricultural development,

particularly in potassium-deficient regions. Among the various potassium-bearing minerals, potassium feldspar ($KAlSi_3O_8$) has attracted considerable attention due to its wide distribution, vast global reserves, and high concentrations of economically important elements, chiefly potassium and alumina. (Lü et al., 2018) However, recovering potassium from insoluble minerals like K-feldspar is much more expensive than extracting it from soluble sources. This is mainly because extra processing is needed to change the potassium into a form that can dissolve in water. These steps often require high temperatures, high pressure, and the use of chemical or biological additives, which increase both energy use and production costs. (Chen et al., 2024)

The primary challenge in extracting potassium from minerals like K-feldspar lies in their complex structure, where potassium ions are tightly bound within the silicate lattice through strong Al–O and Si–O bonds. As a result, potassium in these minerals has very low or almost no solubility in water or weak solutions. (S. Jena et al., 2014; Yuan et al., 2015; Zhang et al., 2012) To overcome this challenge, several chemical processing methods have been developed to release the potassium. Common techniques include acid leaching, hydrothermal treatment, (Hongwen et al., 2015; Liu et al., 2015; Santos et al., 2015; Su et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2018) roast-leaching, (Gan et al., 2016; Haseli et al., 2019; Haseli et al., 2020; S. Jena et al., 2014; S. Jena, N. Dhawan, S. Rath, et al., 2016; Santos et al., 2016; Xie et al., 2013; Ye et al., 2014; Yuan et al., 2015; Zhang et al., 2012; Zhong et al., 2017) and bioleaching. Although K-feldspar represents a promising alternative source of potassium, its application remains limited and requires further research to evaluate its practical feasibility, agronomic effectiveness, and potential environmental impacts.

This review provides a systematic analysis and comparative evaluation of four major methods for potassium extraction from K-feldspar. Although extensive research has been conducted on these techniques, the cooperative effects of different fluxing agents—particularly in the hydrothermal and roast-leaching processes—are rarely addressed in the existing literature. This

review aims to evaluate the roles, synergistic effects, and underlying mechanisms of various fluxing agents on potassium extraction efficiency. It also explores the application of statistical optimization methods for determining the optimal processing conditions to achieve maximum potash recovery. The insights provided in this review are expected to contribute significantly to the advancement of sustainable and efficient potassium extraction technologies from K-feldspar.

Why is K-Feldspar Stable

K-feldspar (chemical formula: KAlSi_3O_8) is rich in valuable elements such as potassium (K), aluminum (Al), and silicon (Si), typically containing 5–15% K_2O , 15–25% Al_2O_3 , and 55–65% SiO_2 . (Shi et al., 2023) However, the inherent chemical inertness of K-feldspar, resulting from its highly stable three-dimensional Al–Si–O tetrahedral framework, significantly hinders the dissociation of KAlSi_3O_8 into free K^+ ions, thereby limiting its solubility and bioavailability in aqueous or soil environments. (Skorina & Allanore, 2015; Zhong et al., 2017) The tetrahedral framework of K-feldspar provides substantial physical and chemical stability, making it highly resistant to weathering and chemical attack—even under strong acidic or alkaline conditions at room temperature and atmospheric pressure. (Shi et al., 2023) The melting point of K-feldspar ranges from approximately 1100 °C to 1500 °C, depending on its polymorphic form and geological provenance. Owing to its robust crystalline structure, the efficient extraction of potassium from K-feldspar necessitates the application of substantial thermal energy, often in combination with suitable chemical additives, to effectively disrupt Al–Si–O matrix and promote the liberation of soluble K^+ ions. (Chen et al., 2024).

Currently, the primary methods for extracting potassium from K-feldspar can be broadly classified into three main approaches: (1) the roast-leaching method, which involves the high-temperature thermal decomposition of K-feldspar in the presence of fluxing agents, followed by water or acid leaching to recover soluble potassium compounds; (2) the

hydrothermal method, which employs elevated pressures and moderate temperatures in aqueous environments to facilitate the breakdown of the mineral lattice and the subsequent release of potassium ions; and (3) the acid leaching method, which utilizes strong mineral acids such as sulfuric acid, hydrochloric acid, or fluosilicic acid to dissolve potassium-bearing phases. In addition to conventional chemical and thermal techniques, microbiological methods have been explored for the extraction of potassium from K-feldspar. These approaches utilize specific microorganisms capable of solubilizing potassium through biochemical processes. Furthermore, recent studies have reported the use of ultrasonic pretreatment as a promising method to enhance the extraction efficiency by improving mineral accessibility and accelerating the dissolution of potassium-bearing phases. This is explained in detail below.

Representative Methods for Extracting Potassium from K-Feldspar

Acid Leaching Method

Acid leaching method is widely used technique for separating potassium-bearing minerals based on differences in surface hydrophobicity. Acid leaching involves using fluorine-containing additives—such as fluorite, hexafluorosilicic acid, or ammonium fluoride—together with sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4) or hydrochloric acid (HCl) to extract potassium. These additives help generate hydrogen fluoride (HF) as an intermediate product. HF can react with silicon to form silicon tetrafluoride (SiF_4) and effectively break down the structure of insoluble potassium-containing ores at low temperatures (50–100 °C), allowing potassium to be extracted with an efficiency of 80–97%. (Li et al., 2025; Liu et al., 1993; Malghan, 1976)

Ding et al (Z.W. Ding et al., 2014) explored potassium extraction from K-feldspar via acid hydrothermal treatment. The study evaluated the effects of sulfuric acid concentration, hexafluorosilicic acid dosage, temperature, and reaction duration. Among these factors, sulfuric acid concentration had the most significant impact, followed by temperature and

hexafluorosilicic acid addition. Under optimal conditions, the maximum leaching rate of water-soluble potassium reached 87%, underscoring the effectiveness of acid hydrothermal processing.

Phosphogypsum (PG) is a waste material made during the production of phosphoric acid. It mainly contains $\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. In China, over 80 million tons are produced every year [1]. PG has harmful substances like phosphorus, fluorine, and some chemicals, which make it hard to use. These substances can also pollute the environment and harm people's health. (Lu et al., 2021) Li et al. (Li et al., 2024) investigated a coupled synergistic leaching process involving phosphogypsum (PG) and potassium feldspar using hydrofluoric acid (HF) within a sulfuric acid medium. (Figure 1) This integrated approach aimed not only to enhance potassium extraction from PF but also to facilitate the recovery of phosphorus (P) from PG, offering a dual-benefit route for resource utilization. The process achieved excellent results, with leaching efficiencies exceeding 93% for potassium and 96% for phosphorus under optimal conditions. These results underscore the potential of combined acid-fluoride systems to efficiently decompose complex mineral structures, enabling high recovery rates of valuable elements from refractory ores and industrial by-products.

Figure 1. Acid Leachin Experimental Device

Source: Li et al., 2024

Calcium fluoride (CaF_2) plays a crucial role in acid leaching systems, as it reacts with hydrochloric acid (HCl) to produce hydrofluoric acid (HF)—the only acid capable of effectively breaking down the stable silica (SiO_2) framework

in potassium-bearing ores. In the extraction of potassium from phosphorus–potassium associated ores, the reaction proceeds via a liquid–solid mechanism governed by both chemical kinetics and diffusion. Within the HCl– CaF_2 system, HCl first reacts with CaF_2 and fluorapatite to generate HF. The HF then attacks and decomposes potassium feldspar, releasing soluble potassium ions (K^+) into the solution. HCl is often preferred in this process due to its strong reactivity, cost-effectiveness, and widespread availability as a by-product of various chemical industries. (Haseli et al., 2023) In a subsequent study, Zhou et al. (Zhou et al., 2020) conducted a detailed investigation into the batch leaching behavior of a phosphorus–potassium associated ore using an HCl– CaF_2 system at temperatures ranging from 60 to 90 °C. Their study found that potassium was preferentially leached over aluminum, even though both elements are primarily hosted within the potassium feldspar matrix. This selective dissolution is attributed to the formation of secondary aluminum-containing phases, such as amorphous aluminosilicates, which are less soluble. Additionally, the potential formation of insoluble aluminum–fluoride complexes (e.g., AlF_3) may further inhibit aluminum release, contributing to the observed selectivity in potassium extraction. Ma et al (Ma et al., 2017) investigated the leaching kinetics of K-feldspar using an H_2SO_4 – CaF_2 system combined with ultrasonic treatment. They achieved over 83% potassium dissolution under optimal conditions. The application of ultrasound significantly enhanced leaching by generating cavitation, which promoted microfractures and improved mass transfer. Furthermore, the activation energy was reduced from 72.33 kJ/mol to 55.67 kJ/mol in the 60–90 °C range, effectively increasing the reaction rate and overall efficiency.

Li et al., (2023) investigated the acid leaching of K-feldspar using a combined system of sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4) and ammonium fluoride (NH_4F), proposing an ionization–hydrolysis model to describe the potassium extraction process. Under optimized conditions, the potassium dissolution efficiency reached 76%, highlighting the synergistic effect of NH_4F in enhancing

leaching efficiency by disrupting the aluminosilicate matrix. Further optimization revealed that using finely ground ore (95.64 wt% < 0.074 mm) at 160 °C with 6 mL of H₂SO₄ and 0.5 g·g⁻¹ NH₄F enabled efficient conversion of water-insoluble potassium into soluble forms, driven by initial ion exchange followed by spontaneous mineral decomposition in the 298–433 K range.

Gao et al., (2021) studied potassium extraction from a phosphorus–potassium associated ore containing fluorapatite (Ca₅(PO₄)₃F) and potassium feldspar (KAlSi₃O₈). Using 5 mL of 70 wt% H₂SO₄ alone yielded a 75.3 wt% extraction rate. However, the addition of 0.15 g of CaSO₄ significantly increased the rate to 95 wt.%, demonstrating the catalytic role of calcium salts in promoting the breakdown of the feldspar structure and enhancing potassium recovery.

The acid leaching method effectively disrupts the K-feldspar structure and enables high potassium recovery; however, its broader application is increasingly constrained by high operational costs and serious environmental and health hazards, particularly due to the use of hydrofluoric acid (HF), which leads to equipment corrosion, toxic gas emissions, and hazardous waste production. Despite these challenges, acid leaching has gained renewed interest for two key reasons: it operates at relatively low temperatures (below 120°C) with potassium recovery rates exceeding 90%, and it allows for the simultaneous extraction of other valuable elements—such as phosphorus, aluminum, iron, calcium, and magnesium—from complex ores while limiting silica dissolution. (Zhou et al., 2020)

Hydrothermal Method

The hydrothermal method extracts potassium from K-feldspar by heating the ore with alkaline substances like NaOH, CaCl₂, or Ca(OH)₂ in a sealed, high-pressure container. These additives release hydroxyl ions (OH⁻), which help break the bonds in the mineral's structure, freeing potassium ions (K⁺) into the solution. This process usually takes place at temperatures between 150–300 °C and can recover up to 90% of the potassium. Compared to other methods,

the hydrothermal method is considered more sustainable because it uses less mineral resources and energy, makes better use of potassium ore, and produces less pollution.

Single-Additive Systems

Common additives such as NaOH, KOH, or Ca(OH)₂ release hydroxyl ions (OH⁻), which help exchange cations like K⁺, Ca²⁺, and Na⁺ in the mineral. This cation exchange process breaks down the Al–O–Si and Si–O–Si bonds in the mineral structure, leading to the formation of aluminum hydroxide ions (Al(OH)₄⁻) and hydrated silica (SiO₂·H₂O) on the surface of the minerals.

Sodium hydroxide (NaOH) has been widely studied for the hydrothermal decomposition of K-feldspar. Wang et al (Wang et al., 2012) investigated the reaction between potassium feldspar and NaOH under hydrothermal conditions. Their findings indicated that the potassium extraction rate was most influenced by the NaOH concentration, followed by the reaction temperature and then reaction time. Under optimal conditions, a potassium extraction rate of up to 70% was achieved. Ma et al (Ma et al., 2016) further explored this process by synthesizing acicular wollastonite and aluminum hydroxide through the hydrothermal treatment of K-feldspar with NaOH. Under optimized conditions—specifically, a NaOH-to-K-feldspar mass ratio of 0.60, a temperature of 260 °C, and a reaction time of 2 hours—the extraction efficiencies of K₂O and SiO₂ reached 93.2% and 62.5%, respectively. The NaOH effectively disrupted the feldspar crystal structure, facilitating the formation of a new reaction phase.

Liu et al., (2015) conducted a comprehensive study comparing the reactivity of various alkalis (NaOH, KOH, and Ca(OH)₂) with K-feldspar under hydrothermal conditions, using both powdered and bulk forms of the mineral. Ca(OH)₂ exhibited the highest reactivity, forming several new solid phases, including a potassium-bearing calcium–aluminum–silicate–hydrate (C-A-S-H) phases, which show potential as sustainable, locally sourced fertilizers. (Ciceri et al., 2020) Further work by Liu et al. characterized the hydrothermal reaction

products between K-feldspar and $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$. Apart from carbonates such as potassium carbonate, calcite, and bütschliite, the major products were calcium (alumino)silicates—specifically grossular, tobermorite, α -dicalcium silicate hydrate, and amorphous calcium silicate hydrate. (Figure 2)

Figure 2. Hydrothermal Dissolution Mechanism of K-Feldspar from 130 °C to 250 °C

Source: Liu et al., 2019

These transformations occurred within the temperature range of 130 °C to 250 °C and at K-feldspar-to-lime mass ratios of 7:3 to 3:7, corresponding to Ca/Si molar ratios between 0.72 and 3.91.

Wu et al., (2022) developed a hydrothermal process utilizing KOH, followed by leaching with ammonium hydrogen sulfate (NH_4HSO_4), to enhance the extraction of potassium from K-feldspar. Complete decomposition was achieved at hydrothermal temperatures above 280 °C and reaction times exceeding 120 minutes. Su et al. (Su et al., 2016) proposed a novel hydrothermal method combining KOH and H_2SO_4 to produce potassium sulfate and zeolite NaA from K-feldspar ore. Initially, K-feldspar was converted into kalsilite using KOH at 280 °C. Subsequently, potassium oxide (K_2O) was leached from the kalsilite with an efficiency of 95.73% using 5.5 wt.% H_2SO_4 , a kalsilite-to-acid mass ratio of 6.26, and a leaching temperature of 60 °C for 4 hours. This approach demonstrated a viable route for simultaneous potassium extraction and value-added material

synthesis. Liu et al. (Liu et al., 2016) also evaluated the potassium extraction efficiency from raw K-feldspar through both microwave-assisted hydrothermal (MH) and conventional hydrothermal (CH) methods. Under optimal conditions, highly crystalline merlinoite formed within 60–90 minutes using MH, compared to 6 hours with CH, illustrating that MH can accelerate the reaction rate by 2 to 3 times.

Two-Additive Systems

Li et al., (2025) proposed a synergistic hydrothermal system combining KOH and CaO to enhance the decomposition of K-feldspar and promote the simultaneous release of potassium and aluminum. In this system, structural breakdown of K-feldspar occurs in conjunction with ion exchange between Ca^{2+} and K^+ , reaching equilibrium at an optimal KOH concentration. Under optimal conditions, the leaching rates of potassium, aluminum, and sodium reached 93.63%, 32.94%, and 97.04%, respectively.

Su et al., (2015) investigated the hydrothermal decomposition behavior of K-feldspar in a mixed alkaline system consisting of NaOH and KOH. At a reaction temperature of 240 °C, decreasing the mole fraction of KOH (xKOH) led to the sequential formation of metastable kalsilite, kalsilite, and hydroxyl-cancrinite. At a higher temperature of 280 °C, the metastable kalsilite phase disappeared, the crystallization ranges of kalsilite expanded (xKOH = 1.0–0.4), and hydroxyl-cancrinite formation increased significantly (xKOH = 0–0.2). The decomposition of K-feldspar occurred via OH^- attack, resulting in the release of K^+ , $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_4^-$, and $\text{H}_2\text{SiO}_4^{2-}$, which subsequently crystallized into the observed phases.

Zhao et al., (2019) proposed a novel hydrothermal method utilizing a mixed NaOH–CaO alkaline solution, with microwave pretreatment to enhance the decomposition of K-feldspar and improve potassium extraction. The microwave-assisted pretreatment significantly increased the efficiency of K^+ dissolution, achieving a 95% recovery rate under the same hydrothermal conditions. A low-temperature molten salt method using a NaOH– NaNO_3 mixture was developed to

extract potassium from K-feldspar ore. (Figure 3).

Figure 3. The Schematic Mechanism of Potassium Extraction in the NaOH- NaNO_3 Additive System
Source: Wang et al., 2018

This approach leveraged ion exchange between sodium and potassium ions to enhance potassium recovery and the high potassium recovery rate of 96.25% was achieved. However, it also has some drawbacks, such as low potassium concentration in the liquid after extraction, high energy use for evaporation, and the need for special equipment that can withstand high temperatures, pressure, and corrosion. (Li et al., 2025; Ma et al., 2014)

Roast-Leaching Method

Roast-leaching is one of the most extensively applied methods for potassium recovery from silicate and other potassium-bearing minerals due to its operational simplicity and high extraction efficiency. This method consists of two distinct steps: high-temperature roasting with external additives, followed by water leaching of the ground, roasted material. (Jena et al., 2024) This process use various additives, such as calcium- and sodium-based salts, to react with K-feldspar at high temperatures in specific ratios. This reaction turns the insoluble K-feldspar into water-soluble potassium salts, making it possible to extract potassium. (Samantray et al., 2020; Wang et al.,

2018) Under optimized conditions, the roast-leaching method can achieve potassium extraction efficiencies of 80–95%, especially from potassium-rich minerals such as feldspar. (Jena, 2021b; Santos et al., 2015).

Figure 4. Exchange of Na^+ and K^+ Ion during Roasting; (a) Initial Stage when Na^+ (from Molten NaCl) Ions Enter the Core of Feldspar (b) the Reversal of K^+ to Replace Na^+ (c) the Equilibrium Stage between Na^+ and K^+ Ion
Source: Jena et al., 2024

Single-Additive Systems

Chloridizing roasting offers the highest potassium recovery at the lowest temperature among the proposed methods. (Table 1) It breaks the stable alumino-silicate matrix in feldspar, efficiently releasing potassium and making it the preferred method for extraction. (Jayashree?Samantray et al., 2019) The use of NaCl for potash recovery from K-feldspar has been explored in several studies. When K-feldspar is roasted with NaCl at high temperatures, molten NaCl dissociates into Na^+ and Cl^- ions. The Na^+ ions replace potassium ions (K^+) in the feldspar structure, converting microcline (KAlSi_3O_8) into albite ($\text{NaAlSi}_3\text{O}_8$) through solid-state ion exchange. (Figure 4.) Meanwhile, the Cl^- ions react with the freed K^+ to form potassium chloride (KCl), enhancing potassium extraction, which reached around 61%. (S. Jena, P. Misra, et al., 2016)

Table 1. A General Comparison Review of Roast-Leaching Methods Using Single Additives

Additive	Mass Ratio	Roasting Temperature (°C)	Roasting Time (min)	Efficiency (%)	Reference
NaCl	K-feldspar : NaCl = 1:1	900	60	44	(Sandeep Kumar Jena et al., 2019)
NaCl	K-feldspar : NaCl = 1:1	900	60	61	(S. Jena, P. Misra, et al., 2016)
NaCl	K-feldspar : NaCl = 1:1	900	180	50	(Jena et al., 2024)
NaCl	K-feldspar : NaCl = 1:2.8	900	160	87	(Haseli et al., 2019)
CaCl ₂	K-feldspar : CaCl ₂ = 1:0.8	900	160	90	(Haseli et al., 2019)
CaCl ₂	K-feldspar : CaCl ₂ = 10:17	900	60	≥80	(Jayashree?Samantray et al., 2019)
CaCl ₂	K-feldspar : CaCl ₂ = 1:1.5	850	60	93.41	(Türk & Kangal, 2023)
CaCl ₂	K-feldspar : CaCl ₂ = 1:1	900	60	86	(Sandeep Kumar Jena et al., 2019)
CaCl ₂	K-feldspar : CaCl ₂ = 1:1.15	900	40	91	(Yuan et al., 2015)
CaCl ₂	K-feldspar : CaCl ₂ = 1:0.2	900	40	22	(Yuan et al., 2015)
CaCl ₂	K-feldspar : CaCl ₂ = 1:1.5	850	60	99	(Serdengecti et al., 2019)
CaCl ₂	K-feldspar : CaCl ₂ = 0.65:0.35	900	60	97	(Orosco et al., 2019)
CaCl ₂	K-feldspar : CaCl ₂ = 1:1	900	60	95	(Tanvar & and Dhawan, 2020)
CaCl ₂	K-feldspar : CaCl ₂ = 1:1.5	900	60	98.6	(Türk et al., 2021)
CaCl ₂	K-feldspar : CaCl ₂ = 1:1.8	900	30	99.81	(Samantray et al., 2020)
CaCl ₂	K-feldspar : CaCl ₂ = 1:0.75	900	45	~85	(S. Jena, N. Dhawan, D. Rao, et al., 2016)
CaCl ₂	K-feldspar : CaCl ₂ = 0.55:0.45	900	15	99.6	(S. K. Jena et al., 2014)
CaCl ₂	K-feldspar: CaCl ₂ = 1:1	900	180	92	(Jena et al., 2024)
CaSO ₄	K-feldspar: CaSO ₄ = 1:3	1200	120	62	(Lü et al., 2018)
CaSO ₄	K-feldspar: CaSO ₄ = 1:4	1100	120	~87.7	(Gan et al., 2016)
CaSO ₄	K-feldspar: CaSO ₄ = 1:2	1200	120	~87	(Wang et al., 2014)

Further research by Jena et al. (Sandeep Kumar Jena et al., 2019) using a roast-leach approach confirmed that adding NaCl improves potassium recovery, with the best results (~44%) obtained at 50% NaCl additive. The optimal roasting conditions included 900 °C temperature, 45 µm particle size, 60 minutes roasting, and 15 minutes leaching. Haseli et al. (Haseli et al., 2019) also found that roasting K-feldspar with NaCl at 900 °C yielded a potassium recovery close to 90%, highlighting the effectiveness of NaCl as an additive in potash extraction.

A previous study investigated the use of sodium bicarbonate (NaHCO₃) as an additional additive to reduce the calcination temperature in the roasting process. With 4% NaHCO₃, the potassium extraction efficiency reached 80% at

1200 °C, which is 50 °C lower than the temperature required without the additive; this improvement is attributed to the smaller ionic radius of Na⁺, which lowers the mineral liquefaction point. Furthermore, increasing the NaHCO₃ dosage from 0% to 2%, 4%, and 6% led to a corresponding increase in potassium extraction efficiency from 9.3% to 52.6%, 80.0%, and 89.3%, respectively. (Chen et al., 2024)

Calcium chloride (CaCl₂) has been extensively studied as an effective roasting agent for potassium extraction from feldspar ores due to its ability to facilitate chemical reactions that enhance potassium recovery. Haseli et al. (Haseli et al., 2020) investigated the use of NaCl and CaCl₂ in the thermal decomposition of K-feldspar through experimental approaches

combined with thermochemical equilibrium analysis. Their results demonstrated that CaCl_2 facilitates a higher potassium extraction compared to NaCl under identical conditions. Türk & Kangal (Türk & Kangal, 2023) demonstrated that roasting feldspar with CaCl_2 at a mass ratio of 1:1.5, 850 °C for 60 minutes, achieved a potassium dissolution efficiency of 93.41%. Jena et al. (Sandeep Kumar Jena et al., 2019) reported an 86% potash recovery under slightly different conditions (900 °C, 45 μm particle size, 60 minutes roasting), which significantly outperformed NaCl -based roasting that yielded only 44% recovery.

Yuan et al., (2015) suggested potassium extraction mechanism using CaCl_2 as additive. XRD analyses across multiple studies confirmed the transformation of feldspar minerals into potassium chloride (sylvite), anorthite ($\text{CaAl}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_8$), and other calcium aluminosilicates during CaCl_2 roasting, indicating breakdown of the silicate matrix via thermo-chemical reactions. This transformation facilitates potassium release into soluble forms. Calcium chloride (CaCl_2) was preferred over other chlorides due to the favorable ionic radius of Ca^{2+} (0.99 Å), which is relatively close to that of K^+ (1.33 Å), thereby increasing the probability of effective cation exchange. Furthermore, Ca^{2+} exhibits a greater replacement potential than Mg^{2+} (0.65 Å), not only because of its larger ionic radius but also due to its isoelectronic configuration with K^+ (both having the same electronic structure: $1s^2 2s^2 2p^6 3s^2 3p^6$), which facilitates more efficient ion exchange during the roasting process. Roasting prior to leaching has been consistently shown to be essential for high potassium recovery. (S. Jena, N. Dhawan, S. Rath, et al., 2016)

Serdengecti et al., (2019) emphasized the ineffectiveness of direct leaching, with a roasting-leaching approach yielding up to 99.8% potassium extraction. Similarly, Tanvar and Dhawan (Tanvar & Dhawan, 2020; Tanvar & Dhawan, 2022) reported that planetary ball milling combined with CaCl_2 roasting enhances reaction kinetics, enabling high recoveries (>95%) at lower roasting temperatures. Türk et al. (Türk et al., 2021) developed a method to

produce CaCl_2 from a naturally occurring wollastonite–calcite ore. This in-situ generated CaCl_2 was then mixed with K-feldspar at a 1.5:1 mass ratio and subjected to calcination followed by water leaching, yielding an impressive 98.6% potassium extraction efficiency. A similar approach was taken by Samantray et al. (Samantray et al., 2020), who used waste eggshells—rich in calcite (CaCO_3)—as a low-cost calcium source. After reacting the eggshells with hydrochloric acid to form CaCl_2 , the reagent was employed in the thermal treatment of K-feldspar. Optimal conditions, including a feldspar-to-eggshell ratio of 1:1.8 and roasting at 900 °C for 30 minutes, enabled complete potassium recovery.

Jena, et al., (2016) reported that conventional techniques such as magnetic separation, froth flotation, and inorganic acid leaching yielded a low potash recovery rate of around 8%. However, when a roast-leaching process using calcium chloride (CaCl_2) was applied, the potassium extraction efficiency significantly increased, achieving a recovery rate of over 80%. (Jayashree & Samantray et al., 2019) Further demonstrating the effectiveness of CaCl_2 -based roasting, Jena et al. (S. K. Jena et al., 2014) compared this method to sulfuric acid leaching for potassium extraction from nepheline syenite. The CaCl_2 route, under optimal conditions—45% CaCl_2 , 900 °C roasting, and 15 minutes of water leaching—achieved a potassium recovery rate of 99.6%, significantly outperforming sulfuric acid leaching, which yielded only 60%. Microwave-assisted roasting with CaCl_2 has also demonstrated promising results. According to [34], under optimal conditions—microwave power of 900 W, roasting time of 8 minutes, 20% charcoal, and 30% calcium chloride—potassium recovery rates of 85–88% were achieved. (Jena, et al., 2016)

CaCl_2 outperforms other commercial additives in terms of potassium extraction efficiency. However, its hygroscopic nature adds extra cost to the process. Additionally, recovering KCl from the CaCl_2 – H_2O – KCl leach liquor is energy-intensive, making the overall extraction from K-feldspar more expensive. (Jena et al., 2024)

Lü et al (Lü et al., 2018) examined the roasting and leaching behavior of potassium feldspar (K-feldspar) in the presence of calcium sulfate (CaSO_4). (Figure 5)

Figure 5. Decomposition Mechanism of CaSO_4 during Potassium Extraction

Source: Lü et al., 2018

Their study showed that the reaction initiates above $1000\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, with CaSO_4 decomposition increasing alongside temperature. At a K-feldspar to CaSO_4 mass ratio of 1:3, under 6 MPa pressure, 2-hour duration, and $1200\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, potassium extraction reached 62%, concurrent with 44% CaSO_4 decomposition. While moderate CaSO_4 addition enhanced potassium extraction, excessive amounts diminished reactant contact and increased SO_2 emission, thus suppressing the reaction. Sodium sulfate, a widely used industrial chemical and a major byproduct in various sectors, was selected for its potential to improve process efficiency and contribute to environmental sustainability (Bashpa et al., 2024).

Gan et al., (2016) focused on enhancing potassium extraction from K-feldspar using phosphogypsum ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and elucidated the reaction mechanisms involved. Their findings highlighted a thermal solid–solid reaction, where carbon reduces CaSO_4 to recover sulfur, while K-feldspar reacts with CaSO_4 and CaO , facilitating $\text{K}^+/\text{Ca}^{2+}$ ion exchange and potassium release.

Wang et al., (2014) proposed schematic model illustrating the process. In this model, K^+ ions are exchanged with Ca^{2+} ions, forming potassium sulfate (K_2SO_4). Meanwhile, the

remaining aluminosilicate structure rearranges to maintain charge balance by forming calcium aluminosilicate ($\text{CaAl}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_8$). This compound is then dissolved by H^+ ions derived from carbonic acid (H_2CO_3) dissociation, releasing Ca^{2+} ions. These calcium ions subsequently react with bicarbonate ions (HCO_3^-) to produce calcium carbonate (CaCO_3), facilitating CO_2 sequestration. When conducted under optimal conditions—including a calcination temperature of $1200\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and a CO_2 pressure of 4 MPa—the process achieved potassium extraction and CO_2 mineralization efficiencies of approximately 87% and 7.7%, respectively.

Liu et al. (Liu et al., 2020) optimized a hydrothermal treatment process to produce a potash alternative from K-feldspar and calcium carbonate (CaCO_3). The mixture was first calcined at $1050\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, then subjected to hydrothermal conditions. This process significantly improved the material's solubility. As a result, the K + Al + Si content dissolved in the solution increased by 43% compared to the other samples.

Two-Additive Systems

Beyond single-additive approaches, two-additive systems have been explored to enhance potassium extraction efficiency from K-feldspar. While single-additive system has demonstrated some improvements, growing attention has been directed toward two-additive system, which often exhibit superior performance due to synergistic interactions among their components. Two additive systems such as K-feldspar– CaSO_4 – CaCO_3 , CaCl_2 – NaCl , CaSO_4 – CaCO_3 , PG– NaCl , and PG– CaCO_3 have shown promising results in accelerating reaction kinetics and improving overall potassium yield. (Table 2) Shi et al. (Shi et al., 2023) reported that ternary systems incorporating K-feldspar, chloride salts (e.g., NaCl , MgCl_2 , or CaCl_2), and calcium carbonate (CaCO_3) achieved significantly higher potassium recovery compared to binary systems utilizing either chloride salts or CaCO_3 alone. This suggests that the combination of fluxing agents and thermally reactive additives contributes to more efficient breakdown of the feldspar matrix and facilitates potassium release.

The combination of calcium chloride (CaCl₂) and sodium chloride (NaCl) has been extensively studied for enhancing potassium extraction from feldspar. This Two additive system leverages the high reactivity of CaCl₂ and the economic and handling advantages of NaCl, offering synergistic effects that surpass the efficiency of single-salt systems. Jena et al.(Jena et al., 2024) investigated the impact of combining CaCl₂ and NaCl on potassium recovery from feldspar. Under optimal conditions—feldspar-to-salt ratio of 1:1, roasting temperature of 900 °C, and a roasting duration of 180 minutes—NaCl alone achieved approximately 50% potassium recovery, whereas CaCl₂ reached up to 92%. The reduced efficiency of NaCl was attributed to equilibrium between microcline (KAlSi₃O₈) and albite (NaAlSi₃O₈), influenced by the competitive exchange between K⁺ and Na⁺ ions. Despite the superior extraction performance of

CaCl₂, its hygroscopic nature imposes higher processing costs. However, a mixture containing 40% CaCl₂ and 60% NaCl demonstrated a substantial improvement, achieving 98% potassium recovery at a lower temperature of 850 °C within 60 minutes. This enhanced efficiency was attributed to the formation of albite and anorthite phases, which promote the release of K⁺ as water-soluble KCl. Zhang et al.(Zhang et al., 2012) obtained the potassium extraction rate of 95.35% was achieved using a feldspar: CaCl₂: NaCl mass ratio of 1.8:1.1:0.6, with a particle size of 220 mesh, roasting temperature of 800 °C, and a roasting time of 60 minutes. This study emphasized the importance of optimizing not only the chemical composition of the additive system but also the physical parameters, such as particle size and thermal conditions, to maximize efficiency.

Table 2. A General Comparison Review of Roast-Leaching Methods Using Two Additives

Additive	Mass Ratio	Roasting Temperature (°C)	Roasting Time (min)	Efficiency (%)	Reference
NaCl - CaCO ₃	K-feldspar: NaCl:CaCO ₃ = 1:2:4	900	120	97.29	(Shi et al., 2023)
NaCl - CaSO ₄	K-feldspar: NaCl:CaSO ₄ = 1:1.5:1.25	1000	60	96.08	(Türk & Kangal, 2023)
NaCl - phosphogypsum (PG)	K-feldspar: NaCl:phosphogypsum (PG) = 1:1:1	900	60	92.8	(S. Jena, P. Misra, et al., 2016)
CaCl ₂ - NaCl	K-feldspar: CaCl ₂ :NaCl = 1.8:1.1:0.6	800	60	95.35	(Zhang et al., 2012)
CaCl ₂ - NaCl	K-feldspar: CaCl ₂ / NaCl = 0.5:0.2:0.3	850	60	98	(Jena et al., 2024)
CaCl ₂ - NaCl	K-feldspar: CaCl ₂ : NaCl = 0.5:0.4:0.1	900	180	90	(Haseli et al., 2020)
CaCl ₂ - NaCl	K-feldspar: CaCl ₂ :NaCl = 1:1.25:0.25	850	60	93.71	(Türk & Kangal, 2023)
CaSO ₄ - CaCO ₃	K-feldspar: CaSO ₄ :CaCO ₃ = 1:1:3	1100	40	91.3	(Zhong et al., 2017)
CaSO ₄ - CaCO ₃	K-feldspar: CaSO ₄ /CaCO ₃ = 1:1:3.4	1050	150	~93	(Gan et al., 2016)
Limestone flotation tailing (LFT) - NaCl	K-feldspar: Limestone flotation tailing (LFT):NaCl = 1:0.5:0.75	900	40	97	(Jena et al., 2025)

Shi et al., (2023) investigated that potassium extraction reached 85% at 800 °C in the K-feldspar–CaCl₂–CaCO₃ and K-feldspar–MgCl₂–CaCO₃ systems, while it was only 60% in the K-

feldspar–NaCl–CaCO₃ system under the same conditions. However, increasing the temperature to 900 °C significantly enhanced potassium recovery. In the K-feldspar–NaCl–CaCO₃

system, a recovery rate of 97.29% was achieved at this higher temperature. This was obtained using a mass ratio of K-feldspar: NaCl: CaCO₃ = 1:2:4. Zhang et al. (Zhang et al., 2018) further explored the reaction kinetics between 750 °C and 850 °C conformed to the diffusion-controlled Ginstling–Brounshtein model. A pilot-scale roasting experiment conducted at 850 °C under these conditions yielded a potassium recovery of approximately 82%.

Zhong et al., (2017) investigated the thermal decomposition of K-feldspar in the presence of industrial flue gas desulfurization gypsum waste (CaSO₄) to improve the production of soluble potassium salts. In this reaction system, CaCO₃ decomposes to form reactive CaO, which diffuses into the silicate lattice of K-feldspar owing to the smaller ionic radius of Ca²⁺ (1.00 Å) compared to K⁺ (1.38 Å). This diffusion initiates an ion exchange process that disrupts the KAlSi₃O₈ crystal structure, thereby promoting the release of potassium. Increasing the CaCO₃ content enhances the homogeneity of the reaction mixture and enlarges the contact area between K-feldspar and CaCO₃, facilitating more effective decomposition. The reaction pathway involves the formation of an intermediate phase, Ca₃Al₃Si₃O₁₂ (designated as product layer I), which further decomposes into Ca₂SiO₄ and Ca₃Al₂O₆ (product layer II), resulting in complete structural breakdown and the migration of potassium to the outer layer as K₂SO₄. (Figure 6) Under optimized conditions (1373 K for 40 minutes, with a mass ratio of KAlSi₃O₈: CaSO₄: CaCO₃ = 1:1:3), the process achieved a potassium recovery rate of over 90%, and the resulting K₂SO₄ product attained a purity of 91.3%. Chao et al.(Chao et al., 2013) suggested that KAlSi₃O₈ first decomposed into KAlSi₂O₆, releasing SiO₂, and then reacted with CaO to form intermediates such as unstable K₂SiO₃ at 1200 °C. K₂SiO₃ further reacted with CaSO₄ to produce K₂SO₄.

Türk & Kangal, (2023) evaluated potassium extraction from feldspar using Two additive mixtures of CaCl₂–NaCl and CaSO₄–NaCl. The CaCl₂–NaCl mixture achieved a maximum potassium dissolution efficiency of 93.71% under optimal conditions—850 °C for 60

minutes, with a feldspar: CaCl₂: NaCl mass ratio of 1:1.25:0.25. In comparison, the CaSO₄–NaCl mixture reached a slightly higher efficiency of 96.08% at 1000 °C. Jena, Misra, et al. (S. Jena, P. Misra, et al., 2016) further investigated the use of sodium chloride and phosphogypsum (a by-product primarily composed of CaSO₄) for potassium extraction from feldspar. Sodium chloride served as the chloride source, while phosphogypsum supplied calcium, both of which are critical for effective roasting. When feldspar was roasted at 900 °C using only NaCl, potassium extraction reached 61%. However, the addition of phosphogypsum significantly enhanced recovery, achieving 92.5% extraction.

Figure 6. Double Product Layer Mechanism of KAlSi₃O₈ Decomposition

Source: Zhong et al., 2017

Jena et al., (2025) investigated the use of limestone flotation tailings (CaCO₃) and NaCl to enhance potash recovery from K-feldspar. Acid leaching under optimal conditions extracted only 18–23% of potassium, whereas chlorination roasting with both additives (CaCO₃, NaCl) achieved up to 97% recovery. This high efficiency requires a roasting temperature above the melting point of NaCl to enable effective chlorination and potassium release.

The roast-leach studies using lime mud and NaCl as the additives have been carried out using response surface methodology to optimize the factors for maximizing the potash recovery. (Figure 7)

Under optimum conditions such as a temperature of 950 C, a roasting period of 30min and a ratio of mica: lime mud: NaCl = 1:0.7:0.7, around 99% of the potash value could be recovered.

Figure 7. Three Dimensional Response Surface Plot Showing the Optimization of Potash Recovery
 Source: Jena et al., 2019

Zhao et al., (2020) demonstrated that potassium feldspar (K-feldspar) can be decomposed through high-temperature calcination with limestone and dolomite ($\text{CaMg}(\text{CO}_3)_2$) additives to produce an alkaline mineral Si–Ca–K–Mg fertilizer. At 1250 °C, potassium and silicon extraction ratios reached 83% and 96%, respectively, due to the formation of nanoscale kalsilite crystals and partial melting of leucite into amorphous phases.

However, despite its high efficiency, this method has notable limitations, including high energy consumption because of the latent heat needed to convert potassium from the silicate structure into a liquid-phase salt. (Table 3)

Table 3. Summary of Potassium Extraction Methods for K-Feldspar

Potassium Extraction Methods	Advantages	Disadvantages
Acid leaching method	Low operation temperature and pressure Good system control	Environmental pollution, High reagent cost Equipment corrosion Long reaction time
Hydrothermal method	Low operation temperature Low waste product No solid–liquid separation	High operation pressure Production of complex phases High reagent cost Long reaction time
Roast-leaching method	High potassium recovery Short reaction time Inexpensive molten agents	High water usage High operation temperature
Microbiological methods	Simple and inexpensive process, environmentally friendly Low operation temperature and pressure	Low extraction efficiency Very long reaction time Difficult system control

It also results in increased waste slag generation and demands specialized operational equipment. Furthermore, the use of chlorides and other salts may lead to potential environmental risks. (Haseli et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2018)

Microbiological Methods

Microbiological methods utilize specialized microorganisms to decompose potassium-bearing minerals such as K-feldspar, facilitating the extraction of potassium. The bioleaching process typically involves the secretion of organic and inorganic acids or alkalis by microorganisms, which disrupt Si–O–Si and Al–O bonds in the silicate matrix, leading to structural breakdown and the subsequent release

of potassium (K^+) and sodium (Na^+) ions. Bhattacharya et al. (Bhattacharya et al., 2016) demonstrated that the halophilic bacterium *Acinetobacter soli* (MTCC 5918) exhibited a potassium solubilizing efficiency of 66–68% (w/w) relative to cell dry weight when cultivated using sugarcane bagasse hydrolysate as the carbon source, with an optimal production age of 120 hours. Similarly, Schueler et al. (Schueler et al., 2021) reported that two microbial strains, *Burkholderia* sp. and *Bacillus* sp., isolated from rhizospheric sunflower soil, significantly enhanced potassium release from verdete rock during a 15-day leaching process. When cultured in Aleksandrov medium, these strains improved

potassium extraction by 71.3% and 53.6%, respectively, highlighting their potential as effective bio-solubilizers for agromineral-based potassium recovery.

Despite the environmental friendliness and cost-effectiveness of microbiological methods—particularly for low-grade ores—these approaches present several limitations. These include the need for extensive time and effort to isolate and cultivate effective microbial strains, difficulty in controlling the process once initiated, and the potential generation of toxic byproducts requiring careful management. Additionally, microbiological methods often suffer from relatively low extraction efficiencies and higher operational costs compared to conventional techniques. (Bosecker, 1997; Wang et al., 2018)

Microwave or Ultrasound-Assisted Techniques

Microwave or ultrasound-assisted techniques have gained significant attention as innovative and sustainable methods for enhancing potassium extraction from K-feldspar. Microwave processing enables rapid and uniform heating via dipole rotation and ionic migration, effectively disrupting the crystal lattice and promoting the cleavage of strong Si–O and Al–O bonds that retain potassium within the mineral matrix. (S. Jena, N. Dhawan, S. Rath, et al., 2016)

Liu et al., (2016) found that the microwave-assisted extraction method can enhance the reaction rate by 2–3 times compared to the conventional hydrothermal method. Microwave-assisted roasting followed by water leaching effectively recovered 85–88% of potassium from the unconventional silicate rock under optimal conditions of 900 W microwave power, 8-minute roasting time, 20% charcoal, and 30% calcium chloride. (S. Jena, N. Dhawan, S. Rath, et al., 2016) The selective heating capability of microwave energy allows for efficient activation of mineral phases without necessitating excessively high temperatures, thereby minimizing energy waste and thermal degradation of materials. Furthermore, microwave pretreatment induces localized

thermal stresses and microcracks, which enhance reagent penetration and subsequent leaching efficiency.

Ultrasound-assisted techniques show great promise for potassium extraction from K-feldspar by enhancing leaching efficiency through acoustic cavitation. This process generates shockwaves and micro-jets that promote particle collisions, create surface pores, and improve the penetration of leaching agents into the mineral structure.

Ma et al., (2017) extracted potassium from K-feldspar using an $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4\text{--CaF}_2$ system assisted by ultrasound, achieving a potassium dissolution fraction of over 83% under optimal operating conditions. Recent studies have demonstrated that microwave irradiation can significantly improve extraction kinetics, reduce reaction time, and lower overall energy consumption. Zhang et al. (Zhang et al., 2016) conducted leaching of potassium from phosphorus–potassium associated ore using a sulfuric acid/fluorite system assisted by ultrasound, and the results showed that ultrasound significantly enhanced potassium dissolution, achieving up to 94% under optimal reaction conditions.

Microwave- or ultrasound-assisted techniques, with their reduced environmental impact, offer a promising help to conventional extraction methods. These advanced extraction methods represent a significant step toward cleaner, more efficient, and economically viable potassium recovery processes. (Ma et al., 2017)

Conclusions and Prospects

This review summarizes the mechanisms, effect parameters and efficacy of four methods for potassium extraction from K-feldspar: Acid leaching, Hydrothermal, Roast-leaching and Microbiological methods. Each method has its own advantages and disadvantages in terms of extraction efficiency, energy consumption, ease of operational conditions and environmental protection. Comparison of all these techniques indicates the roast-leaching technique is the best method to recover potash values from mineral sources due to its high efficiency, simple operating procedure and less environmental pollution. Especially, selecting the appropriate

additive can enhance potassium extraction efficiency using roast-leaching method while lowering reaction temperature and time. It also plays a crucial role in reducing equipment costs and minimizing environmental harm from byproducts.

Future prospects lie in improving current technologies to enhance potassium recovery while minimizing energy consumption, operational costs, and environmental impact. Integrated approaches aim to enhance extraction efficiency while reducing costs and energy consumption by combining the use of multiple additives—leveraging their synergistic effects—and incorporating advanced techniques such as ultrasound or microwave assistance into acid or hydrothermal leaching processes. Additionally, the application of statistical optimization and modeling tools can streamline process development and scale-up. Research is also expanding into green technologies, such as bioleaching and recyclable additives, to make potassium extraction more environmentally friendly.

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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